

AN EVALUATION OF FINANCIAL STABILITY AND SOUNDNESS OF THE BANKING SECTOR IN BANGLADESH

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Abstract

This research is an endeavor to assess the soundness of financial health of banking sector through IMF prescribed Core Financial Soundness Indicators Model (FSI) for the selected banks in Bangladesh based on a panel data of 155 Bank-year observations during the time horizon of 2015-2019. This study also assessed how FSIs vary across different groups of banks (State-owned, Conventional Private Commercial Banks (PCBs), Islamic Banks, Foreign Banks, 4th Generation Banks) and impact the stability of banks in Bangladesh. Two separate analysis have been conducted: Core FSI with ANOVA and bank stability with Panel Regression Model. Bank Z Score value was used as a measure of Stability. Variables like Capital Adequacy (CRAR), Asset Quality (NPL), Profitability (ROA & ROE) and Liquidity (LCR & NSFR) were considered as measures of banking soundness. The results show that soundness varies significantly among different groups of banks. The condition of State-owned commercial banks is really perilous as they are burdened with significantly high amount of NPL and lower amount of profit. Only Foreign banks showed better financial soundness in terms of all the chosen FSIs. The results of Panel Fixed Effect Model depict that profitability has strong positive impact on banking stability in Bangladesh. Non-performing loans and liquidity have negative impact on stability. The regression findings also reveal that capital adequacy impacts stability negatively. This negative relation demands a thorough review of the existing capital adequacy requirements of the country's banking sector. These research findings will provide the policy-makers as well as the regulatory authorities with significant policy implications and also help them conduct an in-depth macro-prudential analysis towards a stable financial system. However, these findings require to be interpreted cautiously keeping in mind that these selected FSIs are only some of many other tools such as early warning systems, stress testing and so on.

Keywords : Core Financial Soundness Indicators, Banking Stability, Capital Adequacy, Basel III, Asset Quality, Tier I and II capital, NPL, Liquidity.

1. INTRODUCTION

Financial sector plays a critical role to ensure sustainable economic growth of a country. A sound financial system will facilitate the growth through mobilizing fund for productive investments to the public and private sector, supporting trade and so on.

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(Levine, 1998), (Ross Levine, 2000), (Tabash, 2014). Therefore, financial soundness and stability is an integral part of financial and economic development. Findings of some recent empirical studies (Cristian Valeriu Paun, 2019), (Riley, 2019) confirm the correlation of the development of financial sector and stability and sustainability of high economic growth. Additionally, Bangladesh is alike the most emerging countries where capital market is weak and economy is bank dependent and the banking sector is critical for the sustainable development of the economy as a whole.

However, financial sector has always been exposed to various types of risks and vulnerabilities such as liquidity risks, asset liability duration mismatch, inadequate capital, default risk, market risk and so on. If left unattended, these exposures can result in full-fledged economic crisis. (International Monetary Fund, 2020)

Before hit by the pandemic, the economy of Bangladesh had been growing at an incredible pace of 8.20% in 2019. Recently, Bangladesh has been recommended for its status graduation from the least developed country (LDC) to lower middle-income country with the expectation to graduate to the club of the developed country by 2041. On the contrary, the banking sector of the nation has been facing multiple challenges including weak corporate governance, poor ethical standards, lack of strong and effective leadership, external undue interference in the banking system and so on which caused various types of banking scams and failure, money laundering along with accumulation of huge Non-Performing Loans (NPLs) especially in the state-owned banks and some of the private banks. As an obvious consequence, the performance of the sector is waning. This phenomenon is well reflected in the substantial drop of aggregate profitability of the banking industry over the period of last few years.

Recently the Banking Soundness status of Bangladesh has been published in the Global Competitiveness Report and the country stood at the 130th position out of 141 countries with a score of 38.3 which is the lowest among the South Asian countries. If this trend continues along with the pandemic, it will be difficult to maintain the steady growth rate of the economy. The overall industry performance of the Non-Bank Financial Institutions (NBFIs) is also not very impressive. Also, the contribution of capital market in the financial system is quite insufficient. So, it can be said that even if the country is experiencing a decent economic growth over the last few years, a consistently underperforming financial system may jeopardize the economic development in the long run if it is left unchecked.

Furthermore, the world has been facing an unprecedented crisis on the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic which has created havoc across the global economic and financial domain. Coronavirus has been said to create the biggest threat to the financial systems worldwide similar to the 1920 Great Depression and 2008-09 global financial crisis. IMF estimated the economic cost of the pandemic would total \$28tn in terms of lost output. (Elliott, 2020). Globally, the pandemic triggered the collective

demand, production and spending, trade and economic activities dropped down to the lowest level with the rise of unemployment. As such, worldwide financial institutions have become susceptible to the risk of failure. (International Monetary Fund, 2020)

Facing the adverse impact of COVID-19, our GDP growth rate is expected to further drop down with a sharp economic contraction due to nationwide lockdown, slowdown of economy and obvious spillover effect of pandemic spread. As the banks in Bangladesh have been already struggling with lots of challenges on multiple fronts, this unprecedented situation has added salt to the worsening of the soundness and stability of the sector. Moreover, in accordance with the opinion of the experts, recent policy measure of lending/deposit rate cap may act as another hex to shake the stability of the overall financial system. In this backdrop, it becomes imperative to analyze the soundness of the banking sector's financial health and stability to respond effectively to this crisis with a view to formulating and crafting impactful strategy for future policy development for Bangladesh. In this research, an attempt has been made to evaluate the financial health of selected banks in terms of Financial Soundness Indicators (FSI) as recommended by IMF with a view to finding out the present status of the soundness as well as knowing how soundness differs across the different groups of banks and affects the overall stability of the banking sector in Bangladesh.

1.1 Financial Soundness and Stability: Concept and Indicators

A bank's financial soundness is a condition where the pertinent financial indicators such as capital adequacy, profitability, asset quality, liquidity and so on stand within a certain limit indicating the capability of a financial institute to survive in hostile market conditions or in an economic downturn (Cihak, 2007). Bank soundness is also defined as the ability of a bank to be persistent, solvent and resilient under any unfavorable or negative condition through adequacy of capital and reserve (Swamy, 2014). Financial stability is depicted as the ability of the financial system to facilitate and improve the economy, to manage risks and to absorb any unforeseen losses and shocks. Again, financial instability can be identified by three criteria: 1. when prices of the financial asset deviate or fall sharply 2. functioning of the market and credit availability gets highly contracted and distorted and 3. when aggregate spending gets severely halted. Bank stability persists when individual banks are in a stable condition with no symptoms of banking crisis. The instability in financial system again is the dependence on short-term deposits to fund long-term assets in a less liquid situation.

According to IMF, Financial Soundness Indicators (FSIs) are the indicators that are used to assess financial health and soundness of the banking institutions of an economy. The stability of the financial sector depends largely on the health and soundness of the financial and banking institutions. FSIs, thus, in turn, comprise one of the most crucial parts of macro-prudential analysis of a country. As defined by various literatures, FSIs are statistically measured tools highly effective to oversee and supervise financial sector of a country. Such monitoring of the soundness and health of financial institutions can facilitate early recognition of any likely formation of any

systemic risk that could bring a nation-wide crisis. For this purpose, the financial soundness indicators (FSIs) with specific guidelines were defined and established by IMF. However, the latest financial soundness indicator compilation guide 2019 incorporates the up-to-date international regulatory standards including Basel III reforms to support macro surveillance initiatives to ensure financial stability of a country. The guide established two groups of Financial soundness indicators (FSI)- a core group of 17 indicators and an additional group of 12 indicators for deposit takers or banks to signal out soundness of the financial sector of any economy. The core group incorporates myriads of bank risks, whereas the additional group covers other banking and non-banking financial institution related indicators.

This article intends to analyze the trends of core indicators and determine how financial soundness differs among different groups of banks operating in Bangladesh and investigate how these core FSIs are affecting the stability of our banking industry. For this purpose, some core FSIs have been selected which are relevant for Bangladesh banking industry such as Capital Adequacy, Asset Quality, Profitability and Liquidity. These indicators are also used by Bangladesh Bank to monitor the sector performance from time to time for different analysis of our banking sector's soundness and stability.

Capital adequacy is the size of capital a bank or a financial institution has to hold as required by the regulatory body in order to absorb the potential loss and also to protect the debt holder.

Asset quality is another most critical area in determining the overall soundness of a bank. The prime factor affecting overall asset quality is the quality of the loan portfolios which comprises the major portion of a bank's assets and carries the greatest amount of risk to their capital.

Profitability is the key to success of a well-functioning and reliable banking system. Profitability in banking sector is required to attain stability by nullifying external negative shocks.

Liquidity is a measure of the cash and other assets banks maintain to make payments for a sudden and unanticipated liability including short-term business and financial commitments. To remain viable, a bank must have enough liquid assets to meet such unexpected withdrawals by depositors and other shorter-term obligations.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Financial soundness of Nepalese banks was estimated through Bankometer model for a period of 2007-2012 by Kattel (2015). The study revealed sound financial condition of all banks in Nepal where private sector banks showed better soundness than joint ventures. The study also recommended collaborative effort of bankers and supervisory authority to avoid bank failure. The same Bankometer model was used by Moses O. Ouma (2019) in another research on financial soundness indicators on SME banks in Kenya during 2014 to 2017. Another similar research was conducted

by Suresh N (2019) on financial soundness indicators and banking performance for Bhutan using Bankometer and Dupont analysis. In both the studies, private commercial banks showed better performance in terms of financial soundness than the state owned banks.

Kedar Vijay Marulkar (2017) used Altman Z score model for banking soundness assessment for 40 banks in India and found that Indian banking sector is sound and stable. A causal research was done by Jackson Kiptala Talibong (2019) to determine the influence of soundness indicators (capital adequacy, asset quality, liquidity and investment growth) on the performance of Microfinance banks in Kenya. The research revealed a very strong positive relationship between strong soundness indicators and bank performance. John H. Boyd (1993) conducted a study to find out the key indicators of banking soundness that are highly correlated with bank performance and identified loan size, deposit and capital adequacy as the main indicators. Chang (2016) used IMF's Financial Soundness Indicators (FSI) and analyzed the relationship between FSIs and Business cycle expansion/contraction stages in Taiwan. An advanced research was done by Seyed Ahmad Seyedi (2020) to identify the most effective soundness indicators for the banks of Iran based on expert opinions of senior bankers using descriptive-correlation and TOPSIS method. The study found that indicators that mostly affect the financial soundness are adequacy of capital, asset quality, profitability, liquidity, quality of management and sensitivity to market risk.

From Bangladesh perspective, a study was done by Mohammad M. Uddin (2015) to measure financial soundness of Private Commercial Banks (PCBs) in Bangladesh over a span of 2006-2010. The findings are interesting which revealed that higher deposits, higher assets/loans & advances, more branches and more employees do not bring higher profits for Bangladeshi PCBs. Rahman (2017) made another study on financial soundness indicators based on IMF recommended model for Private commercial banks during 2010-2015 using a Bankometer model. The research revealed that the sampled banks were financially sound and the overall financial system of Bangladesh was stable.

Romualdas Ginevičius (2015) did a soundness and stability test of the banks in Lithuania while using multiple methods including PROMETHEE. This study revealed that soundness and stability situation in commercial banks of Lithuania was fluctuating over the study period. Dominic Gasbarro (2002) assessed the dynamics of financial soundness of the banks in Indonesia during Asian Financial Crisis. This study showed that CAMEL method was successful in portraying the true scenario of banking soundness, but the same CAMEL method failed to depict the real picture during the financial crisis and exhibited significant deviations in key soundness indicators. Ozili P. K. (2018) conducted a research on banking stability in Africa. This study indicated a significant correlation between certain macroeconomic indicators (political stability, government regulation, level of corruption, level of unemployment) and banking stability in African region.

Ching-ChungLin (2016) examined the East Asian Markets and found out that soundness indicators that affect financial stability mostly are asset quality, liquidity, adequacy of capital, profitability and management capability along with favorable economic environment. Another study conducted by Allen N. Berger (1997) investigated the relationships among loan quality, efficiency and capital using Granger-causality technique. He used NPL as a proxy for bank stability. The findings suggested that higher non-performing loans is an indication of the deterioration of cost-income ratio of a bank and increases the possibility of bank failure. Yong Tan (2016) examined the interrelationship between profitability (ROA as proxy) and banking stability (Z-score and stability inefficiency as a proxy) in China over the period 2003-2013 and found that higher stability leads to lower profitability situation in China.

A recent study by Hamed Ahmad Almahadin (2020) focusing on the relationship between financial stability (Z-score) and banking soundness indicators (Capital Adequacy ratio, NPL ratio, growth rate of deposit and domestic credit) in Jordan used FMOLS approach and found that the key indicators have a positive impact on financial growth and stability for Jordanian banks. Another research by Ozili P. (2019) pointed out the factors affecting stability of Nigerian banks while using efficiency, NPL, capital adequacy, concentration and depth of financial system as soundness indicators. This study also found a meaningful relationship between banking stability and soundness indicators.

Ini S. Udom (2015) performed another study to estimate the correlation between financial soundness indicators (asset quality, capital adequacy and income-expenditure based indicators) and financial stability in Nigerian banks and financial system. A detailed study on the financial soundness of the lending sector of Kazakh was conducted by Aigul P. Salina (2019) over the period of 2008 to 2014. The study figured out factors like profitability, capital adequacy, liquidity, asset quality and leverage ratio as the principal components of bank soundness for Kazakh banks. Nicolo (2001) emphasized that banking stability over the long term depends principally on banks' asset utilization and earning generation capacity. Sunday Igbiosa (2020) examined the relationships between capital adequacy and bank stability in Sub-Sahara Africa for 2007-2016 and disclosed similar conclusion.

A research on the stability of the banking sector in European countries for the period of 2004-2014 found that major factors affecting banking stability vary significantly from country to country (Sysoyeva, 2019). Al-Muharrami (2015) used IMF prescribed Financial Soundness Indicators (FSIs) such as asset quality, capital adequacy and liquidity to estimate their impact over the financial stability of Arab GCC deposit taking organizations. A detailed empirical study was done to investigate the relationship between bank stability (Z score as a proxy) and macro-economic variables (GDP, rate of interest and inflation) over a period of 1999-2013 on banking industry of Indonesia applying Autoregressive Distributive Lag (ARDL) and Impulse Response Function method. The study found a noteworthy association between macroeconomic variables and bank stability in case of commercial banks but no relationship for Islamic banks for Indonesia.

Kawsar Jahan (2019) made a detailed study on the determinants of financial stability for Private Commercial Banks in Bangladesh using panel data regression over the period of 2012-2016 and revealed similar conclusions.

3. CONTRIBUTION TO EXISTING LITERATURE

In view of the above discussions, it is clearly evident that although a significant number of global research work on financial soundness and stability enriched the financial market related literature from different perspectives, there are still very few studies focused on the soundness and stability analysis of the financial sector of Bangladesh. Research on assessment of financial soundness using Bankometer model, CAMELS and other statistical tools has been conducted only for private commercial banks of Bangladesh. A very few studies focusing on the state owned and Islamic banks have been undertaken previously. Besides, a limited number of studies were conducted on detecting the determinants of the banking stability for private commercial banks. This research is an endeavor to fill up this gap in the literature. As such, this paper aims to assess the financial health of the banking sector through Financial Soundness Indicators (FSI) assessment prescribed by IMF across the state-owned banks, conventional private commercial banks, Islamic banks, foreign banks and newly established 4th generation banks operating in Bangladesh. Hence, the contribution of this paper is twofold:

- (i) Analyzing the health of the selected groups of banks using IMF recommended Core Financial Soundness Indicators (FSI) and determining whether/how the core FSIs vary across those groups of banks
- (ii) Figuring out how these core FSIs are affecting the stability of the overall banking sector in Bangladesh

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

4.1 Sample design

This study covers the period of 2015-2019 with a random sample of 31 banks comprising a total of 155 Bank-year. Secondary data regarding Core Financial Soundness Indicators (FSIs) have been collected manually from individual annual reports of the respective banks. Following is the summary of the samples:

Table 1 : Summary of Samples

Banks	No of banks	Sample
State-Owned Commercial Banks (SOCB)	6	5
Conventional Private Commercial Banks (Conv-PCB)	23	11
Islamic Private Commercial Banks (Islamic-PCB)	8	5
4th Generation Private Commercial Banks (4th Gen PCB)	10	5
Foreign Commercial Banks (FCB)	9	5
Specialized Banks	3	--
Total	59	31

Source: Bangladesh Bank

Other relevant secondary data and supporting information have been collected from online research or relevant literature research that have been published in newspapers, journals, magazines, online portals, annual reports and other studies etc.

4.2 Methodology for Financial Soundness Indicators (FSIs) Analysis

For analyzing the state of financial soundness following hypothesis has been established and tested through ANOVA (one way) in SPSS.

- Ho: Core Financial Soundness Indicators (FSIs) related to Capital adequacy, Asset quality, Profitability & Liquidity do not vary across groups of banks (SOCB, Conventional PCB, Islamic PCB, 4th Gen PCB & FCB) in Bangladesh
- Ha: Core Soundness Indicators vary across the groups of banks in Bangladesh.

Following Financial Soundness Indicators (FSIs) have been selected for the purpose of analysis:-

- Capital Adequacy ratio - Capital to Risk weighted Asset Ratio (CRAR) (Ozili P. K., 2018), (Al-Muharrami, 2015), (Sysoyeva, 2019), (Nurhuda nizar, 2019), (Kawsar Jahan, 2019)
- Asset quality ratio- Non-performing loan ratio (NPL), (Sysoyeva, 2019), (Al-Muharrami, 2015), (Ozili P. K., 2018), (Nurhuda nizar, 2019)
- Profitability ratio- Return on Asset (ROA) & Return on Equity (ROE), (Sysoyeva, 2019), (Al-Muharrami, 2015), (Nurhuda nizar, 2019)
- Liquidity ratio- Liquidity Coverage Ratio (LCR) & Net Stable Funding Ratio (NSFR). (International Monetary Fund, 2020)

Table 2 : Variables Definition and Measurement

Financial Soundness Indicators (FSIs)	Equation
Capital Adequacy Ratio (CRAR)	Total Regulatory capital /Risk Weighted Asset
NPL ratio (NPL)	Total Non-performing Loan/Total Loans & Advances
Return on Asset (ROA)	Net Profit/Total Asset
Return on Equity (ROE)	Net Profit/Total Equity
Liquidity Coverage Ratio (LCR)	High Quality Liquid Asset/Net Cash Outflow over 30 day period
Net Stable Funding Ratio (NSFR)	Bank's Available Stable Funding/Required Stable Funding

Data Source: (International Monetary Fund, 2020)

All the above-mentioned variables have been collected from the annual reports and disclosures of Basel III for each of these respective banks.

4.3 Methodology for Banking Stability Analysis

For analyzing the impact of Financial Soundness Indicators on the overall stability of the banking sector, panel regression analysis has been conducted using Eviews Software and the following independent and dependent variables have been identified.

4.3.1 Dependent Variable

To measure financial stability, Z-score has been used which is a well-recognized method to measure the banking stability by IMF and World Bank. Again, a sizeable amount of literature has been found to use Z score that set a strong foundation to empirically examine the function of banking soundness over financial stability, particularly in a developing economy like Bangladesh.

Banking Stability (Z score) is calculated using the following formula:

$$Z \text{ Score} = \frac{\text{ROA} + \text{Equity} / \text{Asset}}{\text{S. D (ROA)}}$$

Here, ROA = 5-year moving average of % Return on Total assets of a bank

Equity = Value of Total equity of a bank

Assets = Value of Total assets of a bank

SD (ROA) = 5-year moving average standard deviation of return on assets of the bank.

(Z score Calculation details are given in Appendix B)

Generally, the higher the value of the Z-score, the higher the bank stability or lower the probability of default or failure of the bank. However, as Z-score is highly skewed, for the purpose of this analysis, the natural logarithm of Z-score has been used as it is usually normally distributed and provides a better estimation.

4.3.2 Independent Variables

As the second goal of this study is to determine how the financial soundness indicators (FSIs) affect stability of the banking system in Bangladesh, previously described core FSIs (CRAR, NPL, ROE, LCR) have been used as independent variables for the Regression analysis.

4.3.3 Model Specification

Banking stability has been defined as a function of FSIs for the purpose of analyzing how core FSIs influence banking stability.

Banking Stability = f (Capital Adequacy, Asset Quality, Profitability, Liquidity)..... (1)

(Al-Muharrami, 2015), (Hamed Ahmad Almahadin, 2020), (INI S. UDOM, 2015)

As this study adopts the context and regular structure of panel data analysis, the above functional model can be redefined as follows:

$$\text{Log Z score}_{it} = \alpha_i + \beta_1 \text{CRAR}_{it} + \beta_2 \text{NPL}_{it} + \beta_3 \text{ROE}_{it} + \beta_4 \text{LCR}_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \text{-----} (2)$$

Here,

i refers to the specific bank under consideration

t refers to the year

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4$ are the coefficients of independent variables

α_i is the intercept on independent variables

ε is the error term

CRAR is the Capital Adequacy ratio

NPL is the Non-Performing Loan ratio

ROE is the Return on Equity ratio

LCR is the Liquidity Coverage Ratio

At first, Pooled OLS regression has been conducted which does not take into account the cross-sectional effect of panel data. The White's test of heteroscedasticity revealed that the data sets are not homoscedastic. To deal with this heteroscedasticity and correlation problem, Fixed Effects and Random Effects Models were employed. Then, the Hausman test was conducted to determine the suitable model between fixed and random effect estimates. The Hausman test revealed that Fixed Effect Model is the most suitable for the dataset under consideration.

5. ANALYSIS

The first step is to make a detailed trend analysis of the soundness indicators and then statistical tools were applied.

5.1 Preliminary Analysis of Financial Soundness

From yearly trend of average core FSIs in Figure 1, it is seen that Capital Adequacy measured by CRAR had a steady growth by all selected FCB, Islamic PCB, Conventional PCB & 4th Generation PCB over the last five years and remained above the regulatory requirement of 10 percent (Bangladesh Bank, 2019). This regulatory capital requirement has acted as the major force behind lessening the problem of under-capitalization of banks to a great extent. In contrast, State-owned banks could not maintain the requirement during 2015-17, but the position improved during the last two years mainly due to a reduction in Non-performing loans (Bangladesh Bank, 2019). Additionally, for the newly established 4th Generation banks, CRAR trend is on the decline though they have been maintaining regulatory capital successfully so far. From 2019, banks were instructed to maintain CRAR at 12.50% following international standard and Basel III and all group of banks have been able to meet the requirement except State-owned banks.

Asset quality has shown an appalling outlook over the last five years in selected banks and NPL ratio stood far above the international level of 2%. Over the last five years, all selected Conventional PCBs and Islamic PCBs have shown an upsurge in NPL. As newly established bank, 4th Generation PCBs have a lower NPL relative to other banks, but their trend is also displaying an upward movement like all their counterparts. NPL ratio for the State-owned banks continued to mount sharply at an alarming rate and surpassed all their competitors. The only good news is that the foreign banks were able to maintain a relatively lower NPL.

In line with the poor asset quality, *Profitability* position of the selected banks has shown a downturn during the study period. The State-owned banks' average ROA was negative for the last four years at a stretch which is an obvious consequence of their high level of toxic asset. The ROA trend is also on the decline, yet non-negative for Islamic PCB, Conventional PCB & 4th Gen PCB. Only, average ROA of Foreign banks has displayed a moderate rise. As mentioned already, the most prominent reason behind this low profitability of the banks is the increased amount of Non-performing loans. As per regulation, banks are required to maintain 1.0 percent of the regular loans as provision against income. But for classified loans, provision requirement goes up to 20 percent, 50 percent and 100 percent for Sub-standard, Doubtful & Bad and Loss category respectively. This huge provisioning is eating away the profitability of the banks especially for State-owned banks whose ROA has been experiencing a negative figure. Also, this huge NPL accelerates the operating costs which further reduced the profitability.

Figure 1 : Yearly Movement of Financial Soundness Indicators (FSIs) in Selected banks
 Data Source: Author's calculation based on annual report data

Furthermore, high NPL restricts the lending capacity of banks which becomes less able to provide new credit or productive investments to the economy as evidenced by the continued lower private sector credit growth in Bangladesh. In the long run, this trend may result in an economic slowdown if left unattended.

Figure 2 : Movement of Liquidity measures (LCR & NSFR) in Selected Banks
 Data Source: Author’s calculation based on annual report data

From liquidity trend, it is evident that the selected banks as a whole have been able to maintain the Basel III liquidity requirements– liquidity coverage ratio (LCR) and net stable funding ratio (NSFR) throughout the five-year period on average successfully. The huge peak of NSFR & LCR in State-owned banks during the period is clearly visible from the graph, which has been lowered now. As mentioned earlier, private sector investment trend has not been increased since long, so the banks were bound to invest a major chunk of surplus liquid assets in lower yielding bonds and bills and this has been another cause of their low profitability.

5.2 Statistical Analysis on Financial Soundness Indicators (FSIs)

To determine the variation of the soundness across various groups of banks, ANOVA has been conducted for the sampled data set. As the sample sizes are not equal for the group of banks, homogeneity of variance assumption has been tested with Levene's test is SPSS (details in Appendix A). The result of Levene's test revealed that the groups of banks do not have equal variances which violate the assumptions of Fisher's ANOVA. To resolve this issue, Robust Welch ANOVA test was done that assumes that variances are not equal & a Games Ho-well Post Hoc test was done which is relevant for un-equal variances.

5.2.1 Results & Discussions on Findings of ANOVA & Post Hoc Tests

The following results of ANOVA indicates that for each of the variables i.e. Financial Soundness Indicators, P value of the test statistic in Welch robust test is less than 0.05, thus Ho is rejected at 95% confidence level. The result indicates that Financial Soundness Indicators (FSIs) related to the Capital Adequacy, Asset quality, Profitability and Liquidity differ significantly among Conventional PCB, Islamic PCB, Foreign Banks (FCB), 4th Generation PCB and State-owned Banks (SOCB) in Bangladesh.

Table 3 : ANOVA (One Way) results summary

Variables		Fisher's ANOVA	Welch ANOVA (Robust Test)
CRAR	Statistic	98.498	352.033
	Significance	.000*	.000*
NPL	Statistic	325.324	110.654
	Significance	.000*	.000*
ROA	Statistic	26.541	26.304
	Significance	.000*	.000*
ROE	Statistic	25.373	6.578
	Significance	.000*	0.008*
LCR	Statistic	3.399	9.095
	Significance	0.028**	0.003*
NSFR	Statistic	0.934	6.031
	Significance	0.464	0.013**

* Significant at the 0.01 level **Significant at the 0.05 level

Data Source: Author's calculation based on annual report data

Now, to get further insight on how and in which direction the core FSIs vary, Games-Howell Post Hoc test was carried out. The key findings are below (SPSS output in Appendix A): -

- a. CRAR is significantly high in foreign banks in Bangladesh rather than any other bank category at 99% confidence level. CRAR of 4th generation banks stands at 2nd position after foreign banks at 95% confidence level. However, capital adequacy does not differ significantly among Conv-PCB, SOCB and Islamic-PCB.
- b. NPL is significantly high in State owned banks at 99% confidence level. Among others, 4th Generation banks & foreign banks have the lowest level of NPL. However, asset quality does not differ significantly between 4th Gen & foreign banks. Also, it does not differ significantly between Islamic-PCB & Conventional PCB. The NPL trend can be summarized as: SOCB> Islamic PCB & Conventional PCB>4th Gen & FCB
- c. FCB has a significantly high profitability position in terms of ROA at 99% confidence level. The significant trend of ROA position can be summarized as follows: FCB>4th Generation>Conventional-PCB>Islamic PCB>SOCB
- d. The ROE position roughly does not vary across 4th Gen, FCB, Islamic PCB & Conventional PCB. However, state owned banks have significantly low ROE at 95% confidence level.
- e. Liquidity, in terms of LCR, is higher significantly in 4th Gen banks than Conventional PCB, but does not vary significantly among other categories. Also, NSFR does not vary significantly among group of banks except that 4th Generation banks have higher NSFR level than Conventional PCB.

Overall, it can be summarized that, Foreign and 4th Generation banks have been able to maintain a higher level of regulatory capital in comparison to other groups of banks so far and reported a relatively sound trend in terms of capital adequacy. Again, both FCB and 4th Gen Banks have maintained a comparatively lower level of Non-performing loan and better soundness, in terms of asset quality, relative to other groups. It should be noted here that as a group of newly established bank, 4th generation banks' lower NPL level relative to others is quite expected. But, their NPL is not the lowest rather it is higher than the foreign banks and the trend is threateningly upward which made their asset quality questionable. However, in line with better asset quality & capital adequacy, FCB and 4th Gen Banks have been able to maintain a significantly higher soundness in terms of profitability (ROA) in comparison to other bank groups so far. For liquidity, again these two groups of banks have shown a satisfactory LCR during last five years on average and the trend remained well-above the regulatory requirement of Bangladesh Bank. On the contrary, the state owned banks showed significantly low profitability relative to other group of banks. Their significantly high level of NPL and toxic asset quality was the major reason behind this poor performance.

This stock-pile of huge NPL can lead to the shrinkage in Tier 1 capital in these banks which can ultimately challenge the banks' existence in future. For Liquidity indicators, state owned banks have shown the significant highest trend over the last

five years than any other groups. Apparently, it might be seen as a good indication as they have been able to maintain sufficient liquidity but, this high liquidity can be another reason for their lowest level of profitability. The SOCBs are reported to have surplus cash and idle money at hand for the last few years provided by the declining trend of private sector credit growth in the country.

The soundness indicators have shown to be in the middle ground for the Conventional PCB and Islamic PCB. While their capital adequacy level does not differ significantly with SOCB, their NPL and profitability level stood at a much better position compared to SOCB. These results are also consistent with the previously described yearly trend analysis of FSIs.

5.3 Panel Regression Analysis for Soundness and Stability

To determine the impact of financial soundness indicators on the stability of the overall banking system of Bangladesh, this paper employed Panel data regression analysis.

5.3.1 Descriptive Statistics

The following is a descriptive statistical output of all the variables used in regression.

Table 4 : Descriptive Statistics

	Observations	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness		Kurtosis	
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
CRAR	155	17.345%	11.625%	1.760	0.195	5.480	0.387
NPL	155	8.430%	12.006%	2.664	0.195	6.537	0.387
ROA	155	0.981%	1.217%	-2.221	0.195	15.718	0.387
ROE	155	8.245%	11.965%	-4.487	0.195	27.094	0.387
LCR	155	197.460%	129.649%	2.196	0.195	5.390	0.387
Ln Zscore	153	-128.278%	89.086%	-1.284	0.196	2.877	0.390

Data Source: Author's calculation based on annual report data

5.3.2 Coefficient of Correlation and Multi-Collinearity Analysis

The following table shows the Pairwise Pearson Correlation between the variables. Ln ZScore has positive association with CRAR and ROE and a negative association with LCR and NPL. From this, it can be logically deduced that liquidity and non-performing loans contribute negatively and capital adequacy and profitability contribute positively to the stability of the Bangladeshi banks.

The Correlation matrix shows that the independent variables are not very highly correlated with each other except for 0.828 between ROE and ROA which is above

the cut-off point 0.80 to cause multi-collinearity problem in the regression model. According to (Shrestha, 2020), (Gujarati, 2003), as a rule of thumb, if absolute value of Pearson correlation coefficient is above 0.8, it can be deduced that colinearity is very likely. As a result, the variable ROA has been dropped in the regression model. The 2nd highest correlation is -0.738 between ROE and NPL and it is below the cut-off point 0.80 to cause multi-collinearity. For obtaining more reliable analysis, multi-collinearity diagnostics was done with VIF and Tolerance tests. The table shows that VIF has a maximum value of 2.385 and the lowest value of tolerance is 0.419 which also indicates that there is no problem of collinearity.

Table 5 : Correlation Matrix and Multicollinearity Analysis

Pearson Correlation Matrix							
Variables		CRAR	NPL	ROA	ROE	LCR	LN_Z Score
CRAR	Pearson Correlation	1	-.328*	.555*	.278*	0.080	.475*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	0.320	.000
NPL	Pearson Correlation	-.328*	1	-.647*	-.738*	.256*	-.437*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	0.001	.000
ROA	Pearson Correlation	.555*	-.647*	1	.828*	-0.071	.487*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	0.381	.000
ROE	Pearson Correlation	.278*	-.738*	.828*	1	-.198**	.570*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		0.014	.000
LCR	Pearson Correlation	0.080	.256*	-0.071	-.198**	1.000	-.203**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.320	0.001	0.381	0.014		0.012
LN_Z Score	Pearson Correlation	.475*	-.437*	.487*	.570*	-.203**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	0.012	
Collinearity Statistics							
VIF	1.166	2.385	--	2.232	1.110		
Tolerance	0.858	0.419	--	0.448	0.901		

* Correlation is Significant at the 0.01 level **Significant at the 0.05 level

Data Source: Author's calculation based on annual report data

5.3.3 Findings of Regression Model

The following table shows the empirical model output summary outlined in equations (1-2). Here, the results report two estimates (Pooled OLS and Fixed effect model) of dependent variable i.e bank stability measured by LnZScore. To compare and evaluate between fixed and random effect models of panel regression, the Hausman test was conducted. The resultant p-value (details in Appendix B) is less than 5% indicating that statistically preferred model is fixed effect model over the random effect model for this panel dataset. As a result, random effect model is not reported here.

In summary, the results reveal that for Pooled OLS, the R square and adjusted R square for LnZScore is 45.71% and 44.24% respectively. Also, for fixed effect model (FEM), the values are 78.45% and 72.24% respectively. This indicates that Soundness Indicators (CRAR, NPL, ROE and LCR) contribute 44.24% and 72.24% respectively to the bank stability. Both the models have a p-value < 1% which indicates that models are fit and significant. Again, Wald Test of Coefficient (details in Appendix B) was conducted to examine the joint significance of the independent variables. The p value = 0.000 < 1% indicates that all independent variables are statistically significant predictors of bank stability in Bangladesh.

Table 6 : Panel Regression Analysis

Dependent variable: LnZScore						
	Pooled OLS			Fixed Effect Model		
Independent Variable	Coefficient	t-test	Probability	Coefficient	t-test	Probability
C	-1.943	-12.105	0.000*	-1.172	-4.736	0.000*
CRAR	2.930	5.810	0.000*	-0.968	-0.803	0.424
NPL	0.778	1.126	0.262	-0.941	-0.699	0.486
ROE	3.789	5.618	0.000*	2.695	3.783	0.000*
LCR	-0.110	-2.525	0.013**	-0.042	-1.036	0.302
R-squared	0.4571			0.7845		
Adj. R-squared	0.4424			0.7224		
F-statistic	31.158			12.636		
Prob (F-statistic)	0.000*			0.000*		
Durbin-Watson	0.549			1.529		
Jarque-Bera	2.767			3.169		
Probability	0.251			0.205		
White Chi-Square	43.521			153.00		

Significance	0.000*	0.462
Hausman Chi-square		11.918
Significance		0.018**
Wald Test Chi-square		203.28
Significance		0.000*

* Significant at the 0.01 level; **Significant at the 0.05 level

Data Source: Author's calculation based on annual report data

5.3.4 Discussion on Regression Findings

As illustrated in the Fixed Effect Model in Table 6, among 4 (Four) Financial Soundness Indicators (FSIs), ROE was found to have statistically significant impact on LnZScore or Bank Stability. ROE has significant impact at the level of 1% (p value = $0.00 < 0.01$).

The coefficient of ROE is found to be positive indicating a statistically significant positive impact on Bank Stability which is consistent with the result of pooled OLS model as well. This reveals that the higher the bank profitability, the higher the stability of bank in case of Bangladesh.

However, surprisingly, coefficient of CRAR is negative and insignificant indicating that capital adequacy ratio has a negative effect on bank stability in Fixed Effect Model. But, this negative sign is a total contradiction to the *apriori* expectation. These findings demand further in-depth analysis to investigate the real situation which is out of the scope of this study. However, a possible clarification may lie in the present situation of banking regulation in Bangladesh. Banking Industry of Bangladesh has been implementing Basel II and III phase by phase in recent years. While, overall profitability and stability positions are on the decline for the last few years, due to Bangladesh Bank instruction, banks are in stringent condition to fulfill the capital adequacy level of Basel III. Again, during 2019, some under capitalized banks (State-owned Banks) were specially allowed to maintain their provisioning requirement against Non-performing loans phase by phase by the Bangladesh Bank. As a result, their CRAR position may show an inflated figure although it was not the real scenario.

Further, it is observed that asset quality as measured by NPL has negative coefficient and the impact is not statistically significant. The possible explanation behind this insignificant relation is the value of NPL ratio which is not the proper representation of the true non-performing loan scenario of banking industry of the country. The amount of defaulted loans is considered much higher than what the official figures portray. However, Liquidity measure, LCR has a negative coefficient suggesting that liquidity has a negative impact on stability although the effect is not statistically significant. LCR basically evaluates a bank's strength to survive in a liquidity stressed situation. A possible explanation to this *apriori* relation could be the excess liquidity position of banking sector due to lower private sector credit growth. The

declining credit growth along with excess liquidity led to decrease in the profitability of banks. From correlation matrix, it is also seen that LCR has a negative correlation with ROE. This scenario might make a negative contribution to the overall stability position of the banking sector.

6. SUMMARY OF FINDINGS AND CONCLUDING REMARKS

The main objective of this research was to evaluate the financial health of the banking sector in Bangladesh through analyzing financial soundness indicators (Capital to Risk Weighted Ratio, NPL ratio, Return on Asset and Equity, Liquidity Coverage Ratio, Net Stable Funding Ratio) and determine how this soundness impacts overall stability of the banking system. The results of the study show that soundness level in terms of Capital Adequacy, Asset Quality, Profitability and Liquidity vary significantly among different groups of banks in context of Bangladesh. Further analysis clearly raises concern over financial soundness of the State-owned banks. The performances of SOCB are critically fragile as their profitability level has been significantly low and far below the level of other group of banks. A significant highest level of Non-performing loans in SOCB has been one of the major causes behind their lowest profitability. However, performance of Private commercial banks (both Islamic and Conventional) was relatively sound than SOCB, but again, the NPL trend is on the rise along with declining ROA. Only Foreign banks have been able to show a relatively consistent and significant better financial soundness. Furthermore, applying Pooled OLS and Fixed Effect model, the study empirically analyses the effect of those FSIs to explain the financial stability of the banking industry of Bangladesh. The trend of overall bank stability measured by Z score has also found to be declining over the study period. The findings of regression model have proved that core FSIs are significant to explain the banking stability in Bangladesh. Among other FSIs, ROE was the most vital factor that has a positive effect on the banking sector stability with the highest coefficient. Conversely, it is found that the NPL ratio has negative effect on financial stability although that is insignificant. From a perspective of banking sector performance, this impact is logical which means that due to the increase of non-performing loans, the stability of the banking sector has deteriorated. Liquidity is found to have a negative impact on bank stability. The negative impact is due to the presence of excess liquid asset in our banking industry that has been evidenced due to the lower credit growth for the last few years. The findings also revealed that capital adequacy impacted negatively on the stability. This negative relation has created the scope of reviewing the existing bank capital requirements.

REFERENCES

- Aigul P. Salina, X. Z. (2019). An assessment of the financial soundness of the Kazakh banks. *Asian Journal of Accounting Research*.
- Allen N. Berger, R. (June 1997). Problem loans and cost efficiency in commercial banks. *Journal of Banking & Finance* Volume 21, Issue 6, 849-870.
- Al-Muharrami, S. (2015). The Ability of Financial Soundness Indicators in Assessing the Health of the Financial System: Evidence from Arab Banking. *Proceedings of 10th Annual London Business Research Conference*.
- AT Capital Research. (2020). Bangladesh Banking Sector Report. Retrieved from www.arx.cfa. Bangladesh Bank. (2019). Financial Stability Report. Retrieved from www.bb.govt.bd.
- Chang, Y. (2016). Financial Soundness Indicator, Financial Cycle, Credit Cycle and Business Cycle- Evidence from Taiwan. *International Journal of Economics and Finance*.
- Ching-ChungLin, S.-L. (January 2016). Bank fundamentals, economic conditions, and bank failures in East Asian countries. *Economic Modelling*, Volume 52, Part B, 960-966.
- Cihak, M. (2007). Systemic Loss: A Measure of Financial Stability. *Czech Journal of Economics and Finance*, Vol. 57 Nos 1-2, 5-26.
- Cristian Valeriu Paun, R. C. (2019). The Impact of Financial Sector Development and Sophistication on Sustainable Economic Growth. *Sustainability* 2019, 11(6), 1713
- Dominic Gasbarro, I. G. (2002). The Changing Relationship Between CAMEL Ratings and Bank Soundness during the Indonesian Banking Crisis. *Review of Quantitative Finance and Accounting* volume 19, pages247–260.
- Hamed Ahmad Almahadin, T. K.-K. (2020). Banking soundness-financial stability nexus: empirical evidence from Jordan. *Banks and Bank Systems*, Volume 15, Issue 3.
- INI S. UDOM, O. B. (2015). The Relationship between Financial Soundness Indicators and Financial Stability in Nigeria. *Journal of Money, Investment and Banking*.
- International Monetary Fund. (2020). Global Financial Stability Report. Retrieved from <https://www.imf.org/en/Publications/GFSR/Issues/2020/04/14/global-financial-stability-report-april-2020>
- International Monetary Fund. (2020). International Monetary Fund Bangladesh. Retrieved from International Monetary Fund: <https://www.imf.org/en/Countries/BGD>
- Jackson Kiptala Talibong, E. M. (2019). Financial Soundness Indicators and Financial Performance of Deposit Taking Micro Finance Banks in Kenya. *African Journal of Emerging Issues*, 1(11), 67 - 84.

John H. Boyd, G. D. (2005). The Theory of Bank Risk Taking and Competition Revisited. *The Journal of Finance* Vol. 60, 1329-1343.

John H. Boyd, D. E. (1993). Size and performance of banking firms: Testing the predictions of theory. *Journal of Monetary Economics* Volume 31, Issue 1, 47-67.

Kattel, I. K. (2015). Evaluating the Financial Solvency of Selected Commercial Banks of Nepal: An Application of Bankometer. *Journal of Advanced Academic Research* 1(1):88.

Kawsar Jahan, M. A. (2019). Determinants of Financial Stability: Evidence from Listed Commercial banks in Bangladesh. *DIU Journal of Business and Entrepreneurship* Vol. 12, No. 2.

Md. Enayet Hossain, M. O. (2017). Financial Stability of Islamic and Conventional Bank in Bangladesh: Revisiting Stability measures and Analyzing stability behavior. *Journal of Islamic Monetary Economics and Finance*.

Mohammad Main Uddin, M. A. (2015). Financial Health Soundness Measurement of Private Commercial Banks in Bangladesh: An Observation of Selected Banks. *Journal of Nepalese Business Studies* 9(1):20, December.

Moses O. Ouma, G. N. (2019). Evaluating the Financial Soundness of Small and Medium-Sized Commercial Banks in Kenya: An Application of the Bankometer Model. *International Journal of Economics and Finance Archives* Vol. 11, No. 6.

Nurhuda nizar, A. A. (2019). A Malaysian Banking Stability Index. *International Journal of Accounting, Finance and Business (IJAFB)* Volume:4 Issues: 22.

Ozili K. Peterson, T. G. (2018). Income smoothing among European systemic and non-systemic banks. *The British Accounting Review*, Vol.50 No.5, pp.539-558.

Ozili, P. K. (2018). Banking Stability Determinants in Africa. *International Journal of Managerial Finance*, Vol 14.

Raluca-Ioana Diaconu, D.-C. O. (2014). The Main Determinants of Bank's Stability. Evidence from Romanian Banking Sector. 21st International Economic Conference 2014, IECS 2014, 16-17 May 2014, Sibiu, Romania.

Romualdas Ginevičius, A. P. (2015). The Evaluation of Financial Stability and Soundness of Lithuanian Banks. *Economic Research-Ekonomska Istraživanja*.

Ross Levine, N. L. (2000). Financial intermediation and growth: Causality and causes. *Journal of Monetary Economics*, Volume 46, Issue 1, 31-77.

Seyed Ahmad Seyedi, M. R. (2020). Modeling and Rating Financial Soundness Indicators of Commercial Banks Using Confirmatory Factor Analysis and TOPSIS method. *Iranian Journal of Finance* Volume 3, Issue 3.

Shrestha, N. (2020). Detecting Multicollinearity in Regression Analysis. *American Journal of Applied Mathematics and Statistics*, 2020, Vol. 8, No. 2, 39-42.

Sunday Igbinsosa, F. A. (2020). Capital Adequacy and Bank Stability/Soundness in Sub-Sahara Africa. *European Journal of Accounting, Finance and Investment* Vol. 6, No. 5.

Swamy, V. (2014). Testing the interrelatedness of banking stability measures. *Journal of Financial Economic Policy*, 6(1), 25-45.

Tabash, M. I. (2014). The flow of Islamic finance and economic growth: An empirical evidence of Middle East. *Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 2 (1), 11–19.

Thorsten Beck, O. D. (2013). Bank competition and stability: Cross-country heterogeneity. *Journal of Financial Intermediation* Volume 22, Issue 2, 218-244.

Appendix A

Table A1 : Levene's test of Homogeneity of variance

Variables	CRAR	NPL	ROA	ROE	LCR	NSFR
Levene's Statistic	5.936	2.410	3.420	4.018	2.941	3.699
Significance	0.003*	0.081	0.028**	0.015**	0.046**	0.021**

*Significant at the 0.01 level **Significant at the 0.05 level

Data Source: Author's calculation based on annual report data

Table A2 : Games-Howell Post Hoc Tests Results

Dependent Variable			Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.
Avg. CRAR	4th Gen Bank	Conv-PCB	0.065	0.020	0.123
		FCB	-0.163	0.020	0.004
		Islamic- PCB	0.070	0.020	0.099
		SOCB	0.098	0.023	0.025
	Conv-PCB	4th Gen Bank	-0.065	0.020	0.123
		FCB	-0.228	0.007	0.000
		Islamic- PCB	0.005	0.005	0.882
		SOCB	0.033	0.012	0.149
	FCB	4th Gen Bank	0.163	0.020	0.004
		Conv-PCB	0.228	0.007	0.000
		Islamic- PCB	0.233	0.006	0.000
		SOCB	0.261	0.012	0.000
	Islamic- PCB	4th Gen Bank	-0.070	0.020	0.099
		Conv-PCB	-0.005	0.005	0.882
		FCB	-0.233	0.006	0.000
		SOCB	0.028	0.011	0.232
SOCB	4th Gen Bank	-0.098	0.023	0.025	
	Conv-PCB	-0.033	0.012	0.149	
	FCB	-0.261	0.012	0.000	

		Islamic-PCB	-0.028	0.011	0.232
Avg. NPL	4th Gen Bank	Conv-PCB	-0.036	0.008	0.020
		FCB	-0.003	0.008	0.992
		Islamic-PCB	-0.026	0.007	0.075
		SOCB	-0.287	0.014	0.000
	Conv-PCB	4th Gen Bank	0.036	0.008	0.020
		FCB	0.033	0.006	0.004
		Islamic-PCB	0.010	0.005	0.408
		SOCB	-0.251	0.013	0.000
	FCB	4th Gen Bank	0.003	0.008	0.992
		Conv-PCB	-0.033	0.006	0.004
		Islamic-PCB	-0.023	0.004	0.007
		SOCB	-0.284	0.012	0.000
	Islamic-PCB	4th Gen Bank	0.026	0.007	0.075
		Conv-PCB	-0.010	0.005	0.408
		FCB	0.023	0.004	0.007
		SOCB	-0.261	0.012	0.000
	SOCB	4th Gen Bank	0.287	0.014	0.000
		Conv-PCB	0.251	0.013	0.000
		FCB	0.284	0.012	0.000
		Islamic-PCB	0.261	0.012	0.000
Avg. ROA	4th Gen Bank	Conv-PCB	0.008	0.003	0.230
		FCB	-0.006	0.003	0.411
		Islamic-PCB	0.010	0.003	0.116
		SOCB	0.020	0.004	0.007

	Conv-PCB	4th Gen Bank	-0.008	0.003	0.230
		FCB	-0.014	0.002	0.003
		Islamic-PCB	0.002	0.001	0.040
		SOCB	0.013	0.003	0.044
	FCB	4th Gen Bank	0.006	0.003	0.411
		Conv-PCB	0.014	0.002	0.003
		Islamic-PCB	0.016	0.002	0.002
		SOCB	0.027	0.003	0.001
	Islamic-PCB	4th Gen Bank	-0.010	0.003	0.116
		Conv-PCB	-0.002	0.001	0.040
		FCB	-0.016	0.002	0.002
		SOCB	0.010	0.003	0.084
	SOCB	4th Gen Bank	-0.020	0.004	0.007
		Conv-PCB	-0.013	0.003	0.044
		FCB	-0.027	0.003	0.001
		Islamic-PCB	-0.010	0.003	0.084
Avg. ROE	4th Gen Bank	Conv-PCB	-0.009	0.010	0.879
		FCB	-0.019	0.011	0.506
		Islamic-PCB	-0.011	0.010	0.777
		SOCB	0.173	0.035	0.028
	Conv-PCB	4th Gen Bank	0.009	0.010	0.879
		FCB	-0.010	0.009	0.772
		Islamic-PCB	-0.003	0.007	0.994
		SOCB	0.182	0.034	0.026
FCB	4th Gen Bank	0.019	0.011	0.506	

		Conv-PCB	0.010	0.009	0.772	
		Islamic-PCB	0.007	0.009	0.917	
		SOCB	0.192	0.035	0.019	
	Islamic-PCB	4th Gen Bank	0.011	0.010	0.777	
		Conv-PCB	0.003	0.007	0.994	
		FCB	-0.007	0.009	0.917	
		SOCB	0.184	0.034	0.024	
	SOCB	4th Gen Bank	-0.173	0.035	0.028	
		Conv-PCB	-0.182	0.034	0.026	
		FCB	-0.192	0.035	0.019	
		Islamic-PCB	-0.184	0.034	0.024	
Avg. LCR	4th Gen Bank	Conv-PCB	1.033	0.181	0.003	
		FCB	0.377	0.428	0.893	
			Islamic-PCB	1.028	0.207	0.009
			SOCB	-0.216	0.523	0.992
	Conv-PCB	4th Gen Bank	-1.033	0.181	0.003	
		FCB	-0.656	0.431	0.594	
			Islamic-PCB	-0.005	0.213	1.000
			SOCB	-1.249	0.526	0.269
	FCB	4th Gen Bank	-0.377	0.428	0.893	
		Conv-PCB	0.656	0.431	0.594	
			Islamic-PCB	0.651	0.443	0.616
			SOCB	-0.593	0.653	0.886
	Islamic-PCB	4th Gen Bank	-1.028	0.207	0.009	
			Conv-PCB	0.005	0.213	1.000
		FCB	-0.651	0.443	0.616	

		SOCB	-1.244	0.535	0.276
	SOCB	4th Gen Bank	0.216	0.523	0.992
		Conv-PCB	1.249	0.526	0.269
		FCB	0.593	0.653	0.886
		Islamic-PCB	1.244	0.535	0.276
Avg. NSFR	4th Gen Bank	Conv-PCB	0.091	0.022	0.042
		FCB	-0.060	0.046	0.703
		Islamic-PCB	0.040	0.040	0.837
		SOCB	0.037	0.118	0.997
	Conv-PCB	4th Gen Bank	-0.091	0.022	0.042
		FCB	-0.151	0.042	0.091
		Islamic-PCB	-0.051	0.035	0.624
		SOCB	-0.054	0.116	0.987
	FCB	4th Gen Bank	0.060	0.046	0.703
		Conv-PCB	0.151	0.042	0.091
		Islamic-PCB	0.101	0.054	0.401
		SOCB	0.097	0.123	0.923
	Islamic-PCB	4th Gen Bank	-0.040	0.040	0.837
		Conv-PCB	0.051	0.035	0.624
		FCB	-0.101	0.054	0.401
		SOCB	-0.003	0.121	1.000
	SOCB	4th Gen Bank	-0.037	0.118	0.997
		Conv-PCB	0.054	0.116	0.987
		FCB	-0.097	0.123	0.923
		Islamic-PCB	0.003	0.121	1.000

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Data Source: Author's calculation based on annual report data

Table A3 : Details of Z Score Computation

Z Score value computation for EBL for the year 2016					
Year	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016
ROA	1.72%	1.68%	1.28%	1.32%	1.33%
5 years Moving Average of ROA					1.47%
5 years Standard Deviation of ROA					0.19%
Total Equity/Total Asset ratio					0.0974
Z score value					58.308%

Data Source: Author's calculation based on annual report data

Appendix B

Table B1 : Eviews Output of Pooled OLS regression model

Dependent Variable: LN_ZSCORE

Method: Panel Least Squares

Date: 11/21/20 Time: 10:21

Sample: 2015 2019

Periods included: 5

Cross-sections included: 31

Total panel (unbalanced) observations: 153

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-1.942869	0.160497	-12.10536	0.0000
CRAR	2.930470	0.504353	5.810352	0.0000
NPL	0.777590	0.690350	1.126371	0.2618
ROE	3.789310	0.674513	5.617847	0.0000
LCR	-0.110111	0.043606	-2.525134	0.0126
Root MSE	0.654230	R-squared		0.457144
Mean dependent var	-1.282780	Adjusted R-squared		0.442472
S.D. dependent var	0.890865	S.E. of regression		0.665189
Akaike info criterion	2.054643	Sum squared resid		65.48652
Schwarz criterion	2.153677	Log likelihood		-152.1802
Hannan-Quinn criter.	2.094872	F-statistic		31.15803
Durbin-Watson stat	0.549204	Prob (F-statistic)		0.000000

Data Source: Author's calculation based on annual report data

Table B2 : White Test for Heteroscedasticity for Pooled OLS Model

Chi-Square	df	Sig.
43.521	14	.000

a. Dependent variable: Ln Zscore

b. Tests the null hypothesis that the variance of the errors does not depend on the values of the independent variables.

Table B3 : Eviews Output for Fixed Effect model

Dependent Variable: LN_ZSCORE

Method: Panel Least Squares

Date: 11/21/20 Time: 10:20

Sample: 2015 2019

Periods included: 5

Cross-sections included: 31

Total panel (unbalanced) observations: 153

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-1.172352	0.247535	-4.736111	0.0000
CRAR	-0.968369	1.205649	-0.803193	0.4235
NPL	-0.941248	1.347179	-0.698680	0.4861
ROE	2.694646	0.712219	3.783452	0.0002
LCR	-0.041972	0.040520	-1.035836	0.3024
Effects Specification				
Cross-section fixed (dummy variables)				
Root MSE	0.412176	R-squared		0.784529
Mean dependent var	-1.282780	Adjusted R-squared		0.722444
S.D. dependent var	0.890865	S.E. of regression		0.469340
Akaike info criterion	1.522783	Sum squared resid		25.99300
Schwarz criterion	2.216020	Log likelihood		-81.49287
Hannan-Quinn criter.	1.804387	F-statistic		12.63639
Durbin-Watson stat	1.052981	Prob(F-statistic)		0.000000

Data Source: Author's calculation based on annual report data

Table B4 : White Test for Heteroscedasticity for Fixed Effect Model

Chi-Square	df	Sig.
153.000	152	.462

a. Dependent variable: Ln Zscore

b. Tests the null hypothesis that the variance of the errors does not depend on the values of the independent variables.

Table B5 : Hausman Test

Correlated Random Effects - Hausman Test

Equation: Untitled

Test cross-section random effects

Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	11.917929	4	0.0180

Table B6 : Wald Test

Equation: Untitled

Test Statistic	Value	df	Probability
F-statistic	50.80960	(4, 118)	0.0000
Chi-square	203.2384	4	0.0000

Data Source: Author's calculation based on annual report data